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EVALUATION OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL STABILITY OF DOCETAXEL INCORPORATED NANO STRUCTURED LIPID CARRIER SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Poor physical and chemical stability associated with NLC formulation has been a concern and has taken away the initial attraction in formulating them. Recently it has been reported that the process of lyophilization has been beneficial in improving stability of NLCs (Nanostructured lipid carriers). In the present study Nanostructured lipid carriers of Docetaxel has been formulated using homogenization technique using stearic acid and oleic acid as lipids and soya bean lecithin and poloxamer as surfactant mixture. The optimized lyophilized and non-lyophilized NLCs of Docetaxel formulation was evaluated and compared for its physical stability. From the stability study it can be concluded that process of lyophilization and storage condition significantly influenced the shelf life. The lyophilized product upon storage at 4°C, exhibited a long shelf life of 2.73 years. The shelf life of non-lyophilized product and products stored at room temperature was significantly lower. Hence the study concluded that the process of lyophilization significantly improved the stability of the NLC formulations. The stability results revealed that formulations are found to be stable at 4°C rather than storage at room temp. Based on this, the study recommended that NLCs should be stored at 4°C for the best stability and extended shelf life.

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INTRODUCTION

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) has been attracting lot of attention, in particular with delivery of chemotherapeutic anticancer drugs due to their potential to target to the receptor site at high concentration. [1] Thus an improvement in bioavailability and reduction in adverse side effects is expected to achieve with use of NLCs. But stability issues of NLCs still remains as a point of major concern. [2] Lyophilization has been reported as an approach to improve the physical and chemical stability of NLCs. [3] The rationale for the present study was to formulate an anticancer chemotherapeutic agent, Docetaxel as a NLC formulation. The formulation will be designed so as to make them suitable for administration through intranasal route. By opting this approach, an attempt to target Docetaxel to brain will be tried out for the treatment of brain tumor so as to bypass the blood brain barrier, enhance availability of drug into brain. But along with the superior clinical benefits NLCs are associated with limitations like poor physical stability and shorter shelf life. So in the present part of research work, stability of docetaxel loaded NLCs are evaluated as per ICH guidelines. The effect of lyophilization and storage condition on physical and chemical stability of NLCs will be studied and based on these studies the need for lyophilization to improve stability will be studied. Also the ideal storage condition and shelf life of doetaxel incorporated NLCs will be predicted by conducting accelerated stability studies on the basis of Arrhenius equation. Docetaxel is a semisynthetic side-chain analogue of paclitaxel with antineoplastic property. [4]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Docetaxel was obtained as a gift sample from MacChem Labs Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Chitosan was a kind gift sample from Zydus cadila, Ahmedabad. Stearic acid, Oleic acid, Poloxamer 407 were purchased from Fizmerk India chemicals, Hapur (U.P).

METHODS

Optimization of cryoprotectants [5]

The stress generated during freezing and dehydration process can destabilize the NLC system. To stabilize the NLC during lyophilization, cryoprotectants are to be added. In the optimization trials, 1, 2, 3 and 4% of mannitol were included in the formulations as given in Table no. 1 and evaluated for of its effects on particle size (PS), polydispersity index (PI), encapsulation efficiency (EE) and zeta potential (ZP) of NLC.

EVALUATION OF THE DEVELOPED NANOSTRUCTURED LIPID CARRIERS [6- 9]

Particle size:

The prepared nanostructured lipid carriers were evaluated for particle size, particle size distribution and polydispersity index. The average particle size and polydispersity index measured using a particle size analyzer, Zetasizer (Malvern, UK) based on the principle of dynamic light scattering. In this method, NLC suspension (0.5mL) was diluted 10 folds by dispersing in 5mL of filtered distilled water and the diluted suspension was analyzed for particle size, particle size distribution and polydispersity index.

Zeta potential:

The zeta potential of NLC was measured by using the Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern, UK) based on electrophoretic light scattering. The NLC dispersion was diluted with distilled water (1:100) and mixed to get a uniform dispersion. The zeta potential of this diluted sample NLC was measured at 25°C.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The TEM equipped with combination of bright field imaging, digital imaging and a photography system of 35 mm were used to reveal the morphology and size of the NLCs. To perform the TEM observations, the lyophilized NLCs samples were suspended directly into the distilled water and examined by TEM.

Drug entrapment efficiency

2 ml of drug loaded NLC sample was centrifuged at a speed of 8000 rpm for 45 minutes to separate the lipid and the aqueous phase. The supernatant was then taken, filtered through 40 µm filter paper, diluted with methanol, and the drug content was determined by UV-visible spectrophotometer at 230 nm. The entrapment efficiency of NLC was calculated by:

$$\% EE = [(W_a - W_s) / W_a] \times 100.$$

Where, EE = Entrapment efficiency.

W_a = Amount of Docetaxel added to the formulation.

W_s = Amount of free drug in supernatant.

Drug content [10]

1 ml of each formulation was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted with ethanol to make up the volume to 10 ml. From this solution, 1 ml was taken and further diluted to 10 ml. Absorbance of the prepared solution was measured at 230 nm by using UV-visible spectrophotometer.

Stability studies [11]

Stability studies were done at 4°C and 27°C (Room Temp) for 30, 60 and 90 days as per ICH guidelines

Determination of shelf life [12]

Shelf life at various storage conditions and in presence and absence of lyophilization was determined based on Arrhenius equation by estimating the residual drug content. For this, the optimized DTXL-NLC formulation (NG9) were kept at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 50 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$, $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 50 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ and $50 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 50 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ for three months. Samples were withdrawn and analyzed at specified time intervals 0, 30, 60, and 90 days and the remaining drug content was determined. Samples of zero time were used as controls. Logarithm of percent drug remaining versus time (in months) were plotted. The degradation rate constant 'k' was determined from the slope of the linear line at each experimental temperature using the equation;

$$k = \text{slope} \times 2.303$$

Arrhenius plot was then constructed between the determined log K values at various elevated temperatures against the reciprocal of absolute temperature (1/T). From the Arrhenius plot the degradation rate constant at 25°C (K_{25}) was determined for by extrapolation. The shelf life (T_{90}) for formulation was determined by substituting the value of K_{25} in the following equation:

$$T_{90} = 0.1052 / K_{25}$$

RESULTS

Screening of cryoprotectants

The stress generated during freezing and dehydration process can destabilize the NLC system. To stabilize the NLCs during lyophilization, cryoprotectants are added. Mostly sugars like mannitol are preferred. Mannitol is reported to decrease the osmotic activity of water during crystallization process and also said to prevent particle aggregation which generally occurs during lyophilization. Mannitol provided a smooth and bright texture to lyophilized NLCs. The ease of reconstitution was also better with the presence of mannitol as cryoprotectant. In the trials for optimization of cryoprotectant 1%, 2%, 3% and 4% of mannitol were included in the formulations. Among these batches, formulation F29, with 3% mannitol concentration exhibited better characteristics with particle size of $180\mu\text{m}$, PI of 0.25, %EE of 78% and zeta potential of 41Mv. Hence it has been decided that 3% of mannitol is the optimal concentration as cryoprotectant for the formulation. The results are tabulated in Table no. 1.

Table No. 1: Optimization of cryoprotectant.

Before Lyophilization					
Formulation	Mannitol Concentration	Particle size (μm)	PI	%EE	ZP
F25	0	127	0.19	80.0	42
After Lyophilization					
	Mannitol Concentration	Particle size (μm)	PI	%EE	ZP
F27	1	422	0.81	68.0	
F28	2	280	0.61	76.0	-
F29	3	180	0.25	78.0	
F30	4	205	0.36	76.0	-

Stability studies

Stability studies were done at 4°C and 27°C (Room Temp) for 30, 60 and 90 days. The results of the same are tabulated in Table No: 2. The influence of storage conditions on particle size, PI, % EE and Zeta potential are evaluated. Studies were done on two samples

1. Lyophilized Formulation (NG9)
2. Non Lyophilized Formulation

The following observations were made during study;

Particle size

After 90 days of storage, it was found that in lyophilized product stored at 4°C the particle size slightly increased from $180.10 \mu\text{m}$ to $196.90 \mu\text{m}$, which was not significant. But the same sample when stored at 27°C showed an increase of particle size from $180.10 \mu\text{m}$ to $366.80 \mu\text{m}$ which is significant.

In case of non-lyophilized formulation a significant change in particle size at both storage condition were observed with size increasing from $127.75 \mu\text{m}$ to $418.10 \mu\text{m}$ at 4°C and from $127.75.10 \mu\text{m}$ to $624.70 \mu\text{m}$ at 27°C .

Polydispersity

On storage at 4°C for 90 days, the lyophilized product showed a PI of 0.31, whereas at 27°C PI was slightly raised at 0.41, showing chances more minor initial particle aggregations. This may pattern may progress leading to precipitation of stability problems.

With non-lyophilized formulation it was a significant increase in PI, with 0.65 and 0.89 at 4°C and 27°C respectively indicating aggregation and instability.

Zeta Potential

Zeta potential of 36 was observed for lyophilized product on storage at 4°C after 90 days indicating a stable formulation. Upon storage at room temperature ZP was slightly lowered to 21, showing moderate stability

Stability data of non-lyophilized formulation showed low ZP of 18 at 4°C and 12 at room temperature. The low ZP indicated aggregation of particles.

% Entrapment efficiency

Lyophilized formulation showed a % EE of 72% after 90 days upon storage at 4°C. There was no significant change in % EE when compared to initial value of 78%. But at room temperature % EE lowered to 64%, which is not satisfactory.

In case of non-lyophilized formulation a significant change in % EE at both storage condition were observed with 62% and 60% after 90 days at 4°C and 27°C respectively. The major drop in % EE indicated the instability of absence of lyophilization process.

Table No.2: Stability data of NG9 (Lyophilized & Non-Lyophilized) at 4°C and 25°C.

FORMULATION	STORAGE TEMP	STORAGE PERIOD (DAYS)	PARTICLE SIZE (µm)	PI	ZP	% EE
NG9 (Lyophilized)	4°C	0	180.10	0.25	41	78
		30	186.23	0.28	40	75
		60	191.35	0.30	39	74
		90	196.90	0.36	36	72
	25°C	30	268.45	0.39	29	70
		60	314.25	0.46	24	66
90		366.80	0.52	21	64	
NLC dispersion (Non-Lyophilized)	4°C	0	127.75	0.19	42	80
		30	269.80	0.33	30	71
		60	345.30	0.41	26	66
		90	418.10	0.65	18	62
	25°C	30	324.25	0.58	19	70
		60	448.50	0.71	16	67
90		624.70	0.89	12	60	

Based on stability studies, it can be concluded that the process of lyophilization significantly improved the stability of the formulations. Also the formulations are found to be stable at 4°C rather than storage at room temp.

Determination of shelf life

For determining shelf life, samples were stored at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C. Samples were analyzed at 0, 1, 2 and 3 months for their drug content. The results are reported in Table.3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10. Order of degradation was found to be following a first order pattern. (Fig. 1, 3, 5, 7). To determine the first order degradation rate constant (K) at elevated temperatures, respective Log % of drug remaining was plotted against time (Fig. 1, 3, 5, 7), and the slope of the plot was determined, from which 'K' was determined. The rate of degradation at room temperature K_{25} was determined by plotting $\log K$ v/s $1/T$, followed by extrapolation to $\log K$ at 25°C. The shelf life of the lyophilized and non-lyophilized formulations at 4°C and 25°C were determined and reported in tables no 4, 6, 8, 10 and Fig.9. From the study it can be concluded that process of lyophilization and storage condition significantly influenced the shelf life. The lyophilized product upon storage at 4°C, exhibited a long shelf life of 2.73 years. The shelf life of non-lyophilized product and products stored at room temperature was significantly lower.

Table No.3: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Temp (°C)	Time (months)	Concentration (mg/ml)	Concentration degraded (mg/ml)	%Drug remaining	Log% Drug remaining
30	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.000
	1	19.85	0.15	99.25	1.997
	2	19.68	0.32	98.40	1.993
	3	19.55	0.45	97.75	1.990
40	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.000
	1	19.55	0.45	97.75	1.990
	2	18.95	1.15	94.75	1.977
	3	17.87	2.13	89.33	1.962
50	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.000
	1	19.08	0.92	95.40	1.980
	2	18.03	1.97	90.15	1.955
	3	16.89	3.11	84.45	1.927

Fig No. 1: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Fig No. 2: LOG K VERSUS 1/T FOR LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Table No. 4: DETERMINATION OF SHELF LIFE OF LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Temp (°c)	Degradation reaction rate constant (k)	Log k	Absolute temp (t)	1/t	Shelf life(t ₉₀)
25	0.0032	-2.4882	298	0.0034	
30	0.0078	-2.1079	303	0.0033	32.81 Months
40	0.0292	-1.5346	313	0.0032	(2.73 Years)
50	0.0562	-1.2503	323	0.0031	

Table No. 5: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Temp (°C)	Time (months)	Concentration (mg/ml)	Concentration degraded (mg/ml)	%Drug remaining	Log% Drug remaining
30	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	19.50	0.50	97.50	1.9890
	2	19.08	0.92	95.40	1.9795
	3	18.85	1.15	94.25	1.9743
40	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	19.05	0.95	95.25	1.9789
	2	18.75	1.25	93.75	1.9720
	3	17.55	2.45	87.75	1.9432
50	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	18.08	1.92	90.40	1.9562
	2	17.25	2.75	86.25	1.9358
	3	16.02	3.98	80.10	1.9036

Fig No. 3: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Fig No. 4: LOG K VERSUS 1/T FOR LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Table No. 6: DETERMINATION OF SHELF LIFE OF LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Temp (°c)	Degradation rate constant (k)	Log k	Absolute temp (t)	1/T	Shelf life (t ₉₀)
25	0.0109	-1.9626	298	0.0034	
30	0.0200	-1.6990	303	0.0033	9.63 Months
40	0.0408	-1.3893	313	0.0032	(0.80 Years)
50	0.071	-1.1487	323	0.0031	

Table No. 7: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF NON- LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Temp (°C)	Time (months)	Concentration (mg/ml)	Concentration degraded (mg/ml)	%Drug remaining	Log% Drug remaining
30	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	19.40	0.60	97.00	1.9868
	2	18.88	1.12	94.40	1.9750
	3	18.55	1.45	92.75	1.9673
40	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	18.75	1.25	93.75	1.9720
	2	17.95	2.05	89.75	1.9530
	3	17.05	2.95	85.25	1.9310
50	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	17.38	2.62	86.90	1.9390
	2	16.65	3.35	83.25	1.9204
	3	15.82	4.18	79.10	1.8982

Fig. 5. DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF NON-LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Fig No. 6. : LOG K VERSUS 1/T FOR NON- LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Table No. 8: DETERMINATION OF SHELF LIFE OF NON-LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 4°C.

Temp (°c)	Degradation rate constant (k)	Log k	Absolute temp (t)	1/t	Shelf Life (t ₉₀)
25	0.0158	-1.8003	298	0.0034	
30	0.0253	-1.5969	303	0.0033	6.63 Months
40	0.0520	-1.2840	313	0.0032	(0.55 Years)
50	0.0746	-1.1273	323	0.0031	

Table No. 9: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF NON-LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Temp (°C)	Time (months)	Concentration (mg/ml)	Concentration degraded (mg/ml)	%Drug remaining	Log% Drug remaining
30	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	19.06	0.94	95.30	1.9791
	2	18.08	1.92	90.40	1.9562
	3	17.15	2.85	85.75	1.9332
40	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	17.55	2.45	87.75	1.9432
	2	17.05	2.95	85.25	1.9307
	3	16.25	3.75	81.25	1.9098
50	0	20.00	0.00	100.00	2.0000
	1	16.58	3.42	82.90	1.9186
	2	15.45	4.55	77.25	1.8879
	3	14.52	5.48	72.60	1.8609

Fig No. 7: DETERMINATION OF DRUG DEGRADATION RATE CONSTANT OF NON LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Fig No. 8.: LOG K VERSUS 1/T FOR NON- LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

Table No. 10: DETERMINATION OF SHELF LIFE OF NON-LYOPHILIZED NG9 AT 25°C.

TEMP (°C)	DEGRADATION REACTION RATE CONSTANT (K)	LOG K	ABSOLUTE TEMP (T)	1/T	SHELF LIFE (t ₉₀)
25	0.0350	-1.4564	298	0.0034	3 Months (0.25 Years)
30	0.0514	-1.2890	303	0.0033	
40	0.0652	-1.1858	313	0.0032	
50	0.1032	-0.9863	323	0.0031	

Fig No. 9: COMPARISON OF SHELF LIFE STORAGE CONDITIONS.

CONCLUSION

Based on stability studies, it can be concluded that the process of lyophilization significantly improved the stability of the NLC formulations. The stability results revealed that formulations was found to be stable at 4°C compared to the storage at room temp. Based on this it can be recommended that NLCs should be stored at 4°C. But further clinical studies in animal and human models need to be carried out to establish the safety and efficacy of NLCs for clinical use.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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